

INTERPRETATION OF I. HUSEYNOV'S STORIES

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Abstract. *In the process of teaching Isa Huseynov's stories, the aim is to analyze multicultural values in the analysis of critical opinions about the stories. In addition, in the analysis lessons of the story, the aim is to determine the structure and artistic interpretation of the lesson. If we determine the interpretation of the story "The Path", we can see that we will try to give a general interpretation of the literary criticism about these stories.*

Keywords: *interpretation, commentary, artistic analysis, lyric poems, multi-plot, aesthetic approach, narration.*

Introduction

The concept of interpretation of literary texts determines the theme, idea, main problem and conflict of the work, and expresses the attitude to the work based on the socio-political and aesthetic approaches of the period to which it is related. At the same time, the interpretation of literary texts analyzes multi-plot, complex composition of epic and dramatic works, lyric poems according to their artistic characteristics, and makes generalizations and draws conclusions using various methods (narration, description, demonstration) in oral presentations of literary texts and discussions of artistic examples. In writings of various types, the author justifies his attitude to the theme, problem, and ways of resolving the conflict with consistent evidence, expecting logical sequence, and making generalizations. However, it is to create an interpretation of some of the reader's thoughts about the story through evidence. It is to create an artistic interpretation of a small story belonging to Isa Huseynov's work and to give the reader's interpretation of both criticism and the idea of criticism. It is necessary to take into account a fact about "Trails" that the story consists of two versions. The first version was analyzed with literary criticism and some shortcomings were revealed. The author, having carried out creative work on the work, corrected the shortcomings brought to his attention for the sake of perfect artistic completeness. All this does not overshadow the general artistic merits of the story, does not weaken the impact and pleasure received from the writer's artistic searches. In fact, a critical attitude to certain motifs of the work could not reveal any shortcomings in the scope and drama of the story. The main features of the writer's stylistic direction were formed precisely in his first creative experience. Although in some cases, schematism cannot convey a human character deeply and psychologically, since it is his first creative experience, the habit and ability to benefit from rich traditions manifest themselves. Although the events described by I. Huseynov in the story are seemingly complete, their essence is not understood unambiguously. Behind these complete events, questions are hidden that force the reader to think.

Method

The article was analyzed using the comparative structural method. The main goal is to investigate using the comparative method.

The comments of M. Arif and M. Alioglu on the ideas of literary criticism and the artistic interpretation of the story also arise from these questions. Different views are formed on the facts of life in the story. It should be noted that the critical ideas addressed to the hero of the story are one-sided. Just as the claim of “showing the spiritual power, ennobling effect, and greatness of love” (1) in a short story is not taken seriously, it is also far from objectivity to trivialize the youthful madness of Giyas and Sever’s mutual feelings under the name of “petty feelings”. This idea does not accurately characterize the ideological and artistic direction of “Cries” as a whole. Or it cannot satisfy the reader when G. Khalilov accuses the emotions he experiences from touching his elbows as “light passions” (2.p.50). The psychological elements of the “elbow” contact from the ward form a complete harmony in the reader’s imagination. In this situation, expecting Fuzuli's romantic hero Majnu to exclaim from Giyas, "Go, go, you are not Leyli, oh Parizad," would probably lead to artificiality, and the way the characters express their intimate feelings would seem unnatural. "As we mentioned above, Isa Huseynov reworked the story. After the writer's fruitful work, the story acquired a new content and high artistic quality. In the second version, unlike the previous one, the naturalness in the development of events, the liveliness in dialogue and narration have been restored. The reader's attention is focused on two characters: Sever and Giyas. Sever is a young girl who expects courage and bravery from the boy she loves, hates frivolity, and likes decisive and sharp actions. She expects courage from the boy she loves." (4.p. 51) However, Giyas' cautious actions, his timidity in opening his heart, and his shyness annoy her. Even she herself hints at Giyas several times, but even though the boy's love creates turmoil in her heart, she does not express it. That is why she is offended by Giyas. Although the author does not say it directly, he has artistically justified Giyas's mental states, shyness, and gentleness through indirect means and hints. Giyas is an orphan. He lives under the protection of his uncle. His uncle's wife does not hesitate to hurt him unnecessarily, even addressing him with humiliating words. It is no secret that Sever's mother's address to her as "you orphan" is an obstacle to Giyas's declaration of love for his daughter. On the other hand, this situation stems from his personal psychology and temperament. It is very strange that the writer Ilyas Efendiyev justifies Sever's turning away from Giyas. He believes that the boy is not worthy of love, and this situation cannot be considered typical for modern times in general. He writes: “The youth of today is not the youth of thirty or forty years ago. Now boys and girls do not have much difficulty in expressing their feelings to each other.” How right is it to limit the declaration of love to periods, to measure them from one point of view, such as “the youth of today” (3), without taking into account the individual psychological world of lovers? Is a single, standard method of expressing this sublime feeling possible? Doesn’t love, which remains essentially stable, always show its effect everywhere and to everyone in different ways? In our opinion, the judgment of our esteemed writer about “the youth of today” somehow trivializes our modern youth.

Because “the more people there are on earth, the more types of love there are; everyone loves in a way that suits their temperament, their characteristics, their level of consciousness, and so on. Every love is true and beautiful in its own way; as long as it is not in the head, but in the heart” (3). Therefore, it is not right to put Giyas into the mold of “today’s youth” as an original artistic image. He is speechless when he wants to reveal his pure, true and sincere love. Because he is not like those who open their hearts with all kinds of lies for the sake of false love. Excessive sincerity is directed against Giyas. As it can be seen, it is impossible to agree with I. Efendiyev in such an opinion. Such a formulation and interpretation of the issue does not justify itself.

Therefore, the concept of modern youth is not capable of expressing the aesthetic attitude of the category of "artistic image". By considering the events and facts in the story from a vital and psychological aspect, and clarifying the image from a moral position, other conclusions can be drawn. It is, of course, wrong to define the ideological content of the story as a criticism of the character's practical inactivity. It is also impossible to explain the thoughts that torment Giyas only by his indecision. The indecision in his behavior has more to do with self-doubt, the helplessness arising from his own "orphan" state. These are important facts in revealing Giyas' character, which also reveals the ideological content of the work. They constitute the intellectual direction of the work. Therefore, Giyas is the character that embodies the aesthetic content of the story "Paths". Ilyas Efendiyev, who pays attention to other aspects of the story, writes that there is no dynamism in the images: "We first saw Giyas as shy, as dull in feeling and action as he approaches Sever, so he emerges from the story as he is. Nothing changes in his heart, love, or character. And we are not impressed at all" (3). It is true that in every work of fiction, the internal dynamics and action of the characters are necessary. However, we must not forget that if the story had changed the character of the hero, the work and the image of Giyas would have had an unconvincing, fictional effect. It seems to us that the questions that make the reader think, arising from the logic of events, arise precisely from the described state of Giyas. It gives more food for the reader's thoughts. Let's not go too far. If a qualitative change had occurred in the consciousness of the hero of the classic story "Master Zeynal", if he had even slightly doubted the futility of the religious mentality, the more artificial the work would have had, and if Giyas in "Cryings" had changed from shy nature to bold openness in a short time, it would have been even further from being convincing. The image of Giyas turned out to be dry and schematic. In the example of the story "Paths", one can make such an idea, which is characteristic of I. Huseynov's individual style - line, that although he did not deviate from the tendency to reflect certain established traditions, especially the fate of the same type of person, the process of changing the image, he did not get addicted to stereotyped topics. In addition to benefiting from the experience of our literature on the moral and spiritual searches of man, he deserves to be appreciated for his new tendency in the artistic study of the subject.

In this respect, the author attracts attention for the unique forms of expression of the idea content in the story "Paths". The writer has given preference to the description at the level of his talent from the prism through which he understands the image of Giyas. The author, who has the ability to penetrate the spiritual world of characters with different life paths and different personalities to the same extent, makes suggestive hints at the flaws that Giyas is exposed to, and the reader believes in the future evolution of this image. The development of the image lies in its artistic completeness. Gradually eliminating Giyas' helplessness and turning him into a fighting man would have no role in the artistic solution of the theme. This artistic operation would have been artificial in nature. Because the logical continuation of events is clear, artificiality is alien to the nature and aesthetics of the true story genre. Therefore, "Paths" was not approached with much attention and care as an example of a story. It has been overlooked that Isa Huseynov made a strong attempt to move away from old habits when determining his creative direction, approach to vital facts and assessment style. In order to confirm his own ideas and aesthetic principles, he tried to ignore old norms and outdated stylistic rules. In the example of this story, it is clear that his artistic position does not accept clichés. It should also be noted that sometimes the author, in order to artificially connect the events in the story with social life and labor, undermined the artistic

quality of this lyrical and sincere work by using inappropriate expressions such as "fulfilling the plan ahead of time" and others. It should not be forgotten that the importance of any work for the literary process cannot be measured only by its subject and the production processes in it. It is a fundamentally wrong step to consider and appreciate the establishment of a subject related to any production problem, the detailed reenactment of certain aspects of professional and artistic activity as a path of art, a requirement of craftsmanship. In such a case, the main essence of literature - the human problem - fades into the background. Therefore, the main success of the story is directly related to the fact that it brings to the fore the life and thinking of a living person. Although they are present in a limited way in "Cığırılar", images are not glorified only in a lyrical-romantic manner. Here, the characters are presented more as participants in real everyday events. A typical fragment of reality clarifies the artistic point in a short and simple plot. The colorfulness of artistic paint and lines is characteristic of "Trails" as one of the main indicators of the writer's narrative creativity as a whole. I. Huseynov attaches serious and special importance to the method of presenting moral convictions and spiritual values with specific artistic details. The leading direction of the artistic analysis of the characters is the lyrical-psychological style. The main artistic goal is revealed in the unity of penetration into the inner world of the characters and psychological analysis. In this process, the details are accompanied by precise strokes. The style of "Trails" is also the fruit of this desire and it meets all the requirements of the genre. It is impossible not to mention the idea that in "Trails" the character of the character is revealed against the background of the nature of the events. The environment in which Gıyas lives raises questions in the reader with his mutual relations with the environment, his personal character, and his judgments. This aspect acquires an artistic-stylistic quality characteristic of the character and qualitative innovation of I. Huseynov's prose.

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